

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium as Vanadium(V)-Tartrate Complex

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Vanadium(V) forms with tartrate in slightly acidic medium an orange-red complex which is extracted by tri-*n*-hexylamine solution in chloroform. Vanadium is determined spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance of the complex at 375 nm against a reagent blank. Beer's law is obeyed over the range 4-40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The method is selective as large amounts of chromium, manganese, iron, cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, aluminium, arsenic, cadmium, uranium and alkaline earth elements do not interfere. The tolerance limit of molybdenum, tungsten and titanium is comparatively low. Only trace quantities of zirconium, tin and antimony are tolerated. Platinum and palladium interfere. The method is quite simple and rapid. It has been successfully applied for the analysis of vanadium in a variety of synthetic samples.

SELECTIVE and sensitive methods for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium are of importance because the element occurs in a varied range of concentration in synthetic and natural samples. Many reagents¹⁻⁸ have been suggested for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium but they generally lack selectivity, although some of them⁶⁻⁸ are sufficiently sensitive. Tartaric acid has been found to be a suitable reagent as it gives a selective reaction with vanadium. Vanadium(V) forms an anionic tartrate complex⁹ and its extraction into an organic phase might be accomplished by associating with alkylamines in acidic medium. Various such amines, tribenzylamine, tri-*n*-butylamine, tri-*n*-hexylamine, tri-*n*-octylamine and tri-*iso*-octylamine were tested to extract the complex. Among these, tri-*n*-hexylamine was found to be the best extractant. Vanadium obtained in the orange-red extract was determined spectrophotometrically.

Experimental

A vanadium stock solution (10 mg ml⁻¹ V) was prepared from sodium metavanadate, standardized¹⁰ by titration with iron²⁺, and diluted to 100 and 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Standard stock solutions of other elements (1-10 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water, dilute sulphuric or dilute hydrochloric acid. A 1% (w/v) solution of tartaric acid in distilled water and a 1% (v/v) solution of tri-*n*-hexylamine (THA) in chloroform were made.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the ions to give required compositions.

Procedure: To a nearly neutral sample solution containing 0.1-1 mg of vanadium was added 1 ml tartaric acid solution and pH adjusted to 2-3 with pH meter. The volume was made upto 20 ml with distilled water whose pH had already been adjusted

to the pH of extraction. 10 ml Tri-*n*-hexylamine solution in chloroform was then added to it and shaken for at least 10 sec. After the separation of layers the solvent phase passed through Whatman 41 filter paper (moistened with chloroform) and was collected into a 25 ml volumetric flask (wrapped with carbon paper). The extraction was repeated with another 10 ml THA-CHCl₃ solution. Any complex sticking to the filter paper was washed into the flask with the THA solution before making up the solution to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the orange-red complex was measured at 375 nm in 1 cm silica cells against a similarly prepared reagent blank using Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Samples containing chromium: The sample solution containing chromium(VI) was reduced in sulphuric acid medium (~0.5 N) by adding sodium sulphite solution (5%) dropwise till green colour of chromium(III) obtained. Excess sulphur dioxide was boiled off and after cooling a dilute solution of potassium permanganate was added dropwise till the appearance of permanent pink colour. The excess of potassium permanganate was removed by adding sodium nitrite solution (0.05 M) dropwise till the pink colour discharged with a few drops in excess. Excess of sodium nitrite was removed by adding a small amount of urea. Solution was then shaken vigorously and allowed to stand for 5 min before the proposed determination.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(V) forms coloured anionic complex with tartrate in slightly acidic medium⁹. The extractability of this complex was tested in various alkylamines. Tri-*n*-hexylamine is chosen as the extractant as the absorbance is maximum in THA-CHCl₃. Tri-*n*-octylamine and tri-*n*-butylamine

extract the complex but to a lesser extent, while tribenzylamine and tri-*iso*-octylamine are poor extractants. Solvents like methyl isobutyl ketone, amyl acetate, isoamyl alcohol, butyl alcohol, chloroform, benzene and carbon tetrachloride do not extract the complex. Pretreatment of the tri-*n*-hexylamine with 1-2 *N* sulphuric acid is necessary in order to convert the amine into salt form, otherwise there is a decrease in absorbance even in presence of simple anions *e.g.*, chloride and sulphate. Pretreatment with other acids is not as effective.

Vanadium(V) is known to form anionic⁹ species $[(VO_3)_4(TrH_2)_2]^{4-}$ with tartrate (Tr). The composition of the complex extracted into chloroform is probably $[R_3NH^+]_4 [\{ (VO_3)_4(TrH_2)_2 \}^{4-}]$ and may be presumed to be formed as follows

Spectral characteristics: When the solution containing orange red tartrate complex of vanadium(V) is shaken with THA solution in chloroform, it gets extracted and the absorption spectra of the complex in chloroform is shown in Fig. 1. The complex absorbs very strongly at wavelength shorter than 300 nm and so does the reagent blank. The absorbance of the latter, however, decreases abruptly to a low value at ~ 375 nm, and beyond it diminishes till it becomes negligibly small at wavelength longer than 450 nm. However, the complex shows a small hump at 375 nm which is chosen for measurements. The complex is light-sensitive and hence vessels in which the extracts collected were wrapped with carbon paper. Under these conditions the complex is stable for 72 h. The calibration graph is linear

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of vanadium(V)-tartrate in THA-chloroform.

A— $24 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ V measured against reagent blank.
B—Reagent blank measured against chloroform.

over the range $4-40 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ V with a sensitivity of $0.036 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Effect of variables: The effect of various parameters on the vanadium(V)-tartrate extraction is shown in Table 1. In these studies (except for the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF V(V)-TARTARATE

Tartaric acid soln.(1%), ml	0.3	0.5	1.0-2.0	4.0	8.0
Absorbance	0.790	0.960	1.04	0.925	0.902
pH	1.5	2.0-3.0	3.5	5.0	6.0
Absorbance	0.155	1.04	0.972	0.624	0.30
Equilibration time, min		0.17-3.0	5.0		
Absorbance		1.04	1.03		
THA in $CHCl_3$ (%)	0.5	1.0-1.5	2.0		
Absorbance	0.602	0.722	0.708		

effect of THA concentration) 20 ml aqueous phase containing $50 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ V was extracted with 10 ml 1% THA in chloroform and the absorbance was measured at 375 nm after single extraction. The effect of THA concentration was studied from the aqueous solution containing $30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ V and with two extractions each with 10 ml 1% THA-chloroform. The optimum conditions for maximum absorbance are 1.0-2.0 ml tartaric acid (1%), 2.0-3.0 pH of the aqueous solution, 0.17-3.0 min equilibration time and 1.0-1.5% THA in chloroform.

Effect of diverse ions: The reagent produced no colour with any of the ions tested except platinum and palladium which are not among those elements generally found in vanadium samples. Platinum and palladium interfere seriously giving yellowish-brown and brown extracts, respectively. Large amounts of molybdenum and tungsten are not tolerated but these elements do not interfere upto 1 mg amount. Chromium interferes seriously when present as Cr^{VI} , but if kept as chromium(III) (as in the procedure) then its contribution towards absorbance is nil, even in 100 mg amounts. Upto 100 mg each of the nickel(II), cobalt(II), copper(II), manganese(II), zinc(II), aluminium(III), iron(II, III), cadmium(II), beryllium(II), magnesium(II), calcium(II), strontium(II), and barium(II) do not show absorbance at 375 nm, giving colourless extracts in each case. Titanium(IV) forms white precipitate in the pH range of extraction and hinders the phase separation, thus lowering its tolerance limit to 2 mg. Similarly other ions like zirconium, tin and antimony get hydrolysed under the conditions of extraction and hinder seriously in phase separation. These ions can be tolerated to that level where phase separation is not affected.

Applications: The proposed method of determination is selective for vanadium in the presence of large amounts of chromium, manganese, cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, iron, aluminium and uranium, which interfere in several existing methods. The method is quite simple and uses simple reagents. After the preparation of sample solution the determination takes less than 15 min. The use of a

single dense solvent is also an advantage. The method is useful in the analysis of many vanadium containing materials, both natural and synthetic. The scope and applicability of the method is shown by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples (Table 2), without separation or complexation of the elements associated with vanadium. The advantage of the method lies in its selectivity and simplicity.

TABLE 2 ANALYSIS OF SAMPLES BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

Matrix*	Sample composition	V added µg	V found µg
	Cr(50)	400	400, 401
	Ni(60) Co(70)	400	399
	Cu(35) Al(20) Zn(40)	800	598
	U(5) Mn(15) Cu(20)	500	499, 501
	Al(30) Zn(40) Ni(20)	600	599
	Mo(1) W(0.8)	300	300, 301
	Co(25) Mn(10)	400	400
	Cu(61), Zn(93)**	500	500, 501

* The number in brackets indicates mg of element in the aliquot taken for analysis.
** Analogous to vanadium bronze.

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